

Long-Term Changes in Summer Weak Wind Duration and Stagnation Indicators in Tel Aviv (1940–2025)

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Abstract

This study focuses on the practical impacts of climate change rather than theoretical meteorological modeling. By analyzing long-term local trends, this work analysis changes in weak wind patterns affecting urban environments, and serves as a case study for coastal Mediterranean cities.

The publication introduces a procedure for determination of average summer period. The average summer period based on air temperature over the past 11 years is in Tel Aviv from June 6 to October 7, 124 days.

The term “*Weak Wind*” is defined in this work as the rounded-down average wind speed between 1940 and 2025.

The calculations are for various levels of the “*Weak Wind*”, from 10 km/hr to 2 km/hr, each 2 km/hr.

The publication introduces the “*Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator*” (WWSI-S) that quantifies the cumulative annual wind stagnation during the summer. It is calculated as the product of the difference between the baseline weak wind speed (WWBL) and the mean summer weak wind speed (WWS-S) over the cumulative seasonal time (DWW) when wind speeds remain below the threshold.

The analyzed parameters are:

- summer weak wind speed – WWS-S
- summer weak wind duration - DWW
- Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator – WWSI-S
- average continuous hours of summer weak wind – cHr-S
- maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind – MaxcHr-S

In general, the average annual weak wind speed in summer increased slightly over the period 1940–2025 by 0.0025 km/hr per year, contributing to summer thermal comfort.

For the 10 km/hr threshold the annual average summer weak wind increased from 5.5 to 5.7 km/hr.

Long-term data reveal that the annual average of very weak winds in summer below 2 km/hr had a stable horizontal trendline of 1.3 km/hr between 1940 and 2022 (83 years) with a minor annual deviation not exceeding +/-0.10 km/hr. This historical regime changed in the mid-2020s. Since 2023 the deviation from the trendline has increased significantly, reaching +0.16 km/hr in 2023 and -0.21 km/hr in 2025.

Overall, the thermal comfort associated with weak winds in summer improved by 8.5% between 1940 and 2025.

Glossary

Ave	average
cHr-S	annual average continuous hours of summer weak wind, hours
cHr-S(2)	annual average continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=2km/hr, hours
DWW	Summer Weak Wind Duration - cumulative time that the wind speed in summer is below the TWW threshold, hr/summer
MaxcHr-S	annual maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind, hours
MaxcHr-S(2)	annual maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=2km/hr, hours
OWWSI-S	Overall Change in Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicators, %
TL	linear trendline 1940-2025
TWW	Summer Weak Wind Threshold, in this work, multi-threshold framework with stepping spectrum {10, 8, 6, 4, and 2 km/hr}
WWBL	Weak Wind Baseline, in this work, rounded down average wind speed in the period 1940-2025, 10 km/hr
WWS-S	Summer Average Weak Wind Speed, annual mean wind speed below the TWW threshold in summer, km/hr
WWSI-S	Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator - product of year mean difference between Weak Wind Baseline (WWBL) and the summer weak wind speed (WWS-S) below the TWW threshold and the cumulative summer duration (DWW) spent below the same TWW threshold, km/summer
WWSI-S(2)	Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator for 2km/hr threshold - multiplication of the difference between WWBL and WWS-S below 2 km/hr by cumulative summer duration (DWW) spent below the same 2 km/hr TWW, km/summer

Units

Wind speed is in km/hr at 10m above ground.

The data are for Tel Aviv center @32.09139,34.782608.

Ground elevation is 11.0m above sea level.

Time is GMT+2 for the whole year, DST not considered.

Data Source

All data are from “Open Meteo - Historical Weather API” [1]-[5].

Wind speed is at 10m above ground.

Wind speed is at the indicated hour, and not an average of the last hour, km/hr.

Table 1 - Wind speed in Tel Aviv dataset [1]-[5]

from date	01/01/40
to date	31/12/25
years	86
days	31,412
hours	753,888
records	753,888
missing	3
correct	753,885
units	km/hr
resolution	0.1

The first 3 records in the wind speed datasets are missing.

The missing records on 1 Jan 1940 were determined based on the next day wind speed pattern at the relevant hours.

Table 2 - Estimation of missing wind speed records on 1 Jan 1940

hr	02/01/40 km/hr	Δ km/hr	01/01/40 km/hr
0:00	15.8		5.3
1:00	16.6	0.8	6.1
2:00	16.5	-0.1	6.0
3:00	17.4	0.9	6.9

Green – existing records, Red – estimated values

Summer Season

The summer season is defined in this work as the period in which, over the last 11 years (2015-2025), the average air temperature of 10 days was above 25.5°C.

The start date of summer is the first day of the 10-day period, and the end date is the last day of the 10-day period.

The threshold of 25.5°C comes from the publications "*Comfort Heat Index - Thermostatic Control of Air Conditioning Units*" [6] and "*Overcooling Index of Air Conditioning*" [7], which define 25.5°C as the "*Optimal Comfort Heat Conditioning*" (OCAC) temperature that achieves thermal comfort with minimal cooling hours, reduced energy consumption, and a Heat Index (HI) that remains below the Comfort Heat Index (CHI = 26.6°C).

Table 3 - Determination of average summer season in Tel Aviv

	start	end	days
2015	18/05/15	06/10/15	141
2016	30/05/16	05/10/16	128
2017	22/06/17	28/09/17	98
2018	16/05/18	10/10/18	147
2019	16/06/19	28/09/19	104
2020	11/05/20	12/10/20	154
2021	20/06/21	30/09/21	102
2022	16/06/22	05/10/22	111
2023	29/06/23	03/11/23	127
2024	03/06/24	03/10/24	122
2025	16/06/25	09/10/25	115
Min	11 May	28 Sept	98
Ave	06 Jun	07 Oct	123
Max	29 Jun	03 Nov	154
Average Summer	06 Jun	07 Oct	123

Based on the above table, the average summer in Tel Aviv is from 6 June to 7 October, 124 days.

Weak Wind Multi-threshold Framework - TWW

Table 4 - Average wind speed in summer, km/hr

	All year	Summer
Ave	10.93	10.16
rounded down	10.00	10.00
highest TWW		10
WWBL		10

This work applies the multi-threshold framework for summer weak wind speed - TWW.

The highest TWW is determined as the rounded-down average wind speed over the period 1940-2025, 10 km/hr. This value is also applied as the Weak Wind Baseline (WWBL).

Each TWW step is -2 km/hr, resulting in the lowest TWW 2 km/hr, and a stepping spectrum {10, 8, 6, 4, and 2 km/hr}.

In this work, the term "weak wind" (WWS-S) refers to summer wind speeds below the TWW threshold.

Summer Weak Wind Speed – WWS-S

In this work, “*Summer Weak Wind Speed*” (WWS-S) is defined as the annual average summer wind speed calculated exclusively during summer hours, when the wind speed is lower than a selected threshold (TWW).

Chart 1 - Trendlines of annual mean summer weak wind – WWS-S, for the entire spectrum of the TWW threshold, km/hr

Chart 2 - Summer weak wind for TWW=10 km/hr - WWS-S(10), km/hr

In general, the annual average weak wind speed in summer increased slightly in the period 1940–2025 by 0.0025 km/hr per year.

For the 10 km/hr threshold, the annual average summer weak wind (WWS-S(10)) increased from 5.5 to 5.7 km/hr, which contributed to the thermal comfort in summer.

Chart 3 - Summer weak wind for TWW=2 km/hr - WWS-S(2), km/hr

The very weak wind in summer, below 2 km/hr, had a steady horizontal trendline of 1.3 km/hr between 1940 and 2022 (83 years) with a minor annual deviation that did not exceed +/-0.10 km/hr. Since 2023, the deviation from trendline has increased significantly, reaching +0.16 km/hr in 2023 and -0.21 km/hr in 2025.

Table 5 - Contribution of changes in WWS-S to thermal comfort in summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	Contribution to thermal comfort
WWS-S(10)	5.50	5.71	+3.8%	positive
WWS-S(2)	1.28	1.30	+1.3%	positive

The changes in summer weak wind speed had positive impact on thermal comfort.

Summer Weak Wind Duration - DWW

Summer Weak Wind Duration (DWW) is the cumulative time that the wind speed in summer is below the TWW threshold.

Chart 4 - Trendlines of annual Summer Weak Wind Duration - DWW, for the entire spectrum of TWW threshold, hr/summer

Chart 5 - Summer Weak Wind Duration for TWW=10 km/hr - DWW(10), hr/summer

Chart 6 - Summer Weak Wind Duration for TWW=2 km/hr - DWW(2), hr/summer

Table 6 - Contribution of changes in DWW to thermal comfort in summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	Contribution to thermal comfort
DWW(10)	1,478	1,604	+8.5%	positive
DWW(2)	180	117	-35.2%	positive

The above table shows that there was a shift in weak wind in summer from very low speed below 2 km/hr to higher speeds, which had a positive impact on thermal comfort.

Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator – WWSI-S

The Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator (WWSI-S) quantifies the cumulative annual wind stagnation during the summer. It is calculated as the product of the difference between the baseline weak wind speed (WWBL) and the mean summer weak wind speed (WWS-S) over the cumulative seasonal time (DWW) when wind speeds remain below the threshold.

Formula 1 - Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator – WWSI-S, km/summer

$$WWSI-S_k = (WWBL - WWS-S_k) * DWW_k$$

$$k \in \{10,8,6,4,2\}$$

WWSI-S _k	Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator, kilometer per summer,
k	chosen Summer Weak Wind threshold, km/hr
WWBL	Weak Wind Baseline = 10 km/hr
WWS-S _k	summer weak wind speed below k threshold, km/hr
DWW _k	cumulative seasonal duration when wind speeds remain below the k threshold, hr/summer

The stagnation indicator can be explained as the number of kilometers of wind that are missing from the baseline (10 km/hr. If the weak wind was a constant 10 km/hr throughout the summer, the stagnation indicator would be zero.

The higher the wind stagnation, the lower the thermal comfort.

Chart 7 - Trendlines of annual Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator - WWSI-S for the entire spectrum of TWW threshold, km/summer

Chart 8 - Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator for TWW=10 km/hr - WWSI-S(10), km/summer

Chart 9 - Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator for TWW=2 km/hr - WWSI-S(2), km/summer

Table 7 - Contribution of changes in WWSI-S to thermal comfort in summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	Δ/85y	Contribution to thermal comfort
WWSI-S(10)	6,671	6,887	+3.2%	negative
WWSI-S(2)	1,568	1,018	-35.1%	positive

Despite the positive impact of the shift in summer weak wind from very low speed below 2 km/hr to higher speeds, the increase in WWSI-S(10) weak wind stagnation has a negative impact on thermal comfort.

To determine the overall impact on thermal comfort, all thresholds will be included in the integration, all having equal weight (20%).

Formula 2 - Overall Change in Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicators – OWWSI-S, %

$$OWWSI-S = \sum \{ [WWSI-S_k(y2) / WWSI-S_k(y1) - 1] * W_k \}$$

$$k \in \{10,8,6,4,2\}$$

- OWWSI-S Overall Change in Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicators, %
- WWSI-S_k Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator, kilometer per summer for Summer Weak Wind threshold k, km/hr
- k Summer Weak Wind threshold, km/hr
- y1 first year = 1940
- y2 last year = 2025
- W_k weight of WWSI-S_k for each k, %

Table 8 - Overall Change in Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicators – OWWSI-S

	TL 1940	TL 2025	Δ/85y	Integration weight	Integration
WWSI-S(10)	6,671	6,887	+3.2%	20%	+0.6%
WWSI-S(8)	6,316	6,503	+3.0%	20%	+0.6%
WWSI-S(6)	5,243	5,226	-0.3%	20%	-0.1%
WWSI-S(4)	3,594	3,112	-13.4%	20%	-2.7%
WWSI-S(2)	1,568	1,018	-35.1%	20%	-7.0%
OWWSI-S				100%	-8.5%

The overall stagnation indicator has decreased by 8.5% in the last 86 years, which has contributed to thermal comfort.

Continuous Hours of Summer Weak Wind – cHr-S

Chart 10 - Trendlines of annual average continuous hours of summer weak wind – cHr-S - for the entire spectrum of TWW threshold, hours

Chart 11 - Average continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=10 km/hr - cHr-S(10), hours

Chart 12 - Average continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=2 km/hr - cHr-S(2), hours

Table 9 - Contribution of changes in cHr-S to thermal comfort in summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	contribution to thermal comfort
cHr-S(10)	11	12	+4.1%	negative
cHr-S(2)	3	2	-25.1%	positive

Maximum Continuous Hours of Summer Weak Wind – MaxcHr-S

Chart 13 - Trendlines of maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind – MaxcHr-S - for the entire spectrum of TWW threshold, hours

Chart 14 - Maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=10 km/hr - MaxcHr-S(10), hours

Chart 15 - Maximum continuous hours of summer weak wind for TWW=2 km/hr - cHr-S(2), hours

Table 10 - Contribution of changes in MaxcHr-S to thermal comfort in summer

	TL 1940	TL 2025	$\Delta/85y$	contribution to thermal comfort
MaxcHr-S(10)	18	19	+3.8%	negative
MaxcHr-S(2)	9	6	-25.9%	positive

Results Dataset

The dataset of results from this work is publicly available in publication [8].

The dataset includes annual results of all parameters analyzed:

- Summer Weak Wind Speed – WWS-S
- Summer Weak Wind Duration - DWW
- Summer Weak Wind Stagnation Indicator – WWSI-S
- Average Continuous Hours of Summer Weak Wind – cHr-S
- Maximum Continuous Hours of Summer Weak Wind – MaxcHr-S

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